

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B211
Date: 14th June 2006
Take Off 09:38:22
Landing: 12:14:04
Flight Time 2h35m42

Campaign: CAPEX (AEROPOR & VPRACOP)

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Beja Local Area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Martin Glew	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	Filters 1 / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
8	Cloud Physics	Paul James	Met Office
9	Wet Neph / PSAP	Andy Wilson	Met Office
10	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
11	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
12	Core Chemistry	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
13	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
14	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
15	VPRACOP 1 / Radon	Fernando Carvalho	Instituto Tecnológico de Nulcear
16	VPRACOP 2 / Filters 2	Joao Oliveira	Instituto Tecnológico de Nulcear
17	Mission Scientist 2	Daniele Bortoli	University of Evora
18	AEROPOR 1	Frank Wagner	University of Evora
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Flight Track:

B211 Track 14-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b211
 Date: 14 Jun 2006
 Project: CAPEX AEROPOR & VPRACOP
 Location: Beja

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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085556		event	0.68 kft	089	INU to Nav
092713		Start-Up on APU	0.68 kft	089	
092826		Start-Up 4	0.68 kft	089	
093329		event	0.68 kft	089	start taxi
093822		T/O	2.3 kft	185	
094612		jw nev zero	6.0 kft	075	
100023		nev zero	15.0 kft	077	
100053		jw zero	15.0 kft	076	
100059	100553	Run 1.1	15.0 kft	076	
100734	103004	Run 1.2	15.0 kft	240	
100846		event	15.0 kft	234	Heimann cal
103052	103639	Profile 1	15.0 - 9.1 kft	253	
103821	104359	Profile 1	9.2 - 3.6 kft	075	QNH 1010
104847	105223	Run 2.1	3.6 - 3.7 kft	150	
105438	112444	Run 3.1	1.5 - 1.6 kft	239	
105624		event	1.5 kft	236	Heimann cal
112659	112941	Profile 2	1.6 - 4.1 kft	358	
113159	113752	Profile 2	4.1 - 9.0 kft	086	
113753	120019	Run 4.1	9.0 kft	098	
114324		event	9.0 kft	215	Heimann cal
121404		Land	0.70 kft	005	
121908		Shutdown	0.69 kft	116	38 05.13N 7 55.65W

B211 Track 14-JUN-06

B211 LAND EMISS SORTIE BRIEF: June 14th 2006

There are 2 parts to the sortie.

1) LAND EMISS over the Irrigation district of Divor, Portugal.

Defined points in the irrigation area:

- Point 1 – 38 deg 42 min 07.2 secs N, 7 deg 55 min 27.1 secs W
- Point 10 – 38 deg 43 min 37.0 secs N, 7 deg 55 min 26.9 secs W
- Point 13 – 38 deg 43 min 57.2 secs N, 7 deg 54 min 38.3 secs W
- Point 27 – 38 deg 44 min 25.3 secs N, 7 deg 57 min 14.4 secs W

The irrigation district is a 500 ha site with fields of sunflower, tomato, barley, wheat, oats, maize, sorghum, rice, sugar beet and dry land. We will measure the emissivity and other surface properties at as high a spatial resolution as possible.

Weather conditions required

No upper cloud and no low cloud over the irrigation district.

Timings below are relative to the start of the first run over the site

- T-5 Approach point 1 from the S at lowest permitted altitude. Heimann cal, ARIES cals and ARIES zenith view
- T+0 Run through points 1 and 10
- T+1 Make turn while maintaining altitude to approach point 13 from the E. ARIES to store data and do cals and zenith view. Heimann cal.
- T+6 Run through points 13 and 27
- T+7 Make turn while maintaining altitude to approach point 27 from the W. ARIES to store data and do cals and zenith view. Heimann cal.
- T+13 Run through points 27 and 10
- T+14 Make turn while maintaining altitude to approach point 10 from the N. ARIES to store data and do cals and zenith view. Heimann cal.
- T+19 Run through points 10 and 1
- T+20 Make turn while maintaining altitude to approach point 27 from the W. ARIES to store data and do cals and zenith view. Heimann cal.
- T+24 Run through points 27 and 13
- T+25 Make turn while maintaining altitude to approach point 10 from the E. ARIES to store data and do cals and zenith view. Heimann cal.
- T+30 Run through points 10 and 27
- T+31 End mapping

Total time excluding transits 36 mins

2) AEROPOR/VPRACOP near Evora, Portugal.

Weather conditions required

For AEROPOR preferably no cloud. VPRACOP work can be done in any cloud free layers.

The sortie will be a series of racetrack patterns with 5 minute straight and level runs. Racetracks will be stacked vertically. Two racetracks will be performed at each level. Levels will be lowest permitted altitude, in a pollution layer and above the boundary layer, cloud permitting. The racetracks will be located near the ground site at Evora.

Timings below are relative to the start of the first profile.

- T+0 Profile from FL100 to lowest permitted altitude.
- T+15 First racetrack at lowest permitted altitude
- T+30 Second racetrack at lowest permitted altitude
- T+45 Profile upwards to a pollution layer, height to be determined by the mission scientist.
- T+50 First racetrack in pollution layer
- T+65 Second racetrack in pollution layer
- T+80 Profile upwards to above boundary layer, height to be determined by the mission scientist.
- T+85 First racetrack above boundary layer
- T+100 Second racetrack above boundary layer
- T+115 Recover to Beja

Total time excluding transits 115 mins

Take off time will be 1000L. Latest landing is 1300L. If weather conditions are unsuitable for part 1 we will proceed straight to part 2.

Mission Scientist debrief

B211 14th June 2006

LAND EMISS over the Irrigation district of Divor, Portugal. and Aerosols & clear skies (AEROPOR/VPRACOP) flight near Evora, Portugal.

Mission Scientist: Martin Glew

Weather Conditions:

The area was within the flow of a low pressure centre to the SW of Portugal. A severe thunderstorm passed through the area from south to north during the night. Shallow convection appeared over southern Portugal behind the storm during the morning.

Sortie:

Take off was delayed by 30 mins to 0930z due to the nights thunderstorm flooding the ground power unit (21mm fell during the night. Climatic average for Beja during June 2mm) preventing timely provision of aircraft power.

At take off at 093545z rain was falling on the Beja airfield. On the climb out there was scattered stratus as 200ft, ragged shallow Cu at 2000ft, a clear slot 2300ft – 5900ft. The aircraft transited north in cloud at FL060 towards Divor, later climbing to FL100. There was a cloud sheet with tops FL080 with Cu poking through it. It was not possible to see the Divor site so the LAND EMISS was postponed.

We profiled up to FL150 and decided to try and set up a racetrack pattern with 5 min S+L runs for radiation measurements of the lower cloud deck for AEROPOR and filter sampling for VPRACOP. After the first S+L leg of the racetrack cumulus towers forced us off track so the racetrack was abandoned. Instead we maintained FL150, flying S+L where possible but turning to avoid cloud turrets where necessary, picking clearer bits of sky by eye. This manoeuvre was called as a run and was maintained till we had been at FL150 for 30 mins.

We then profiled downwards to FL035 (minimum permitted altitude with ground obscured by cloud) to try and find a cloud free layer at lower altitude. There were cloud layers at FL115, FL090 and FL048 but FL035 was cloudy and there had been no clear slot well enough defined to work with. We proceeded south in cloud till we came out below a layer of Cu with layer cloud above. We attempted to maintain height cloud free at FL035 but failed. We then descended and maintained FL015 for 30 minutes, keeping S+KL for as long as possible but manoeuvring to avoid cloud as was done at FL150. During this time the skies above cleared, leaving us underneath a field of shallow Cu with little other cloud.

We then profiled to get above the shallow Cu layer, settling on FL090 as likely to be cloud free. Cu Nims were seen over Lisbon and to the south. To the east there appeared to be a haze layer at approx. FL100 which was stable enough to inhibit the Cu growth there. At our operating region the Cu began to grow above FL090 so the last part of this run was a series of curves to avoid the Cu turrets.

After 22 mins at FL090 we ran out of budgeted science time and recovered to Beja, briefly passing through the bases of 2 shallow Cu on the way. Landing was at 1214z

Success of flight:

The land emiss part of the flight was aborted. The VPRACOP group got long filter sampling times at 3 levels that were cloud free. AEROPOR got views above and below convective cloud fields.

Instrument status:

SWS: OK

SHIMS: OK

ARIES: OK

MARSS: All channels showing occasional spikes. Mirror bearings showing signs of wear.

Wetneph: OK

Cloud Physics: OK

Core chemistry: Problems with CO and Nox

CVI: OK

CCN: OK

Filters: OK

PSAP: failed

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B211

Date : 14/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

No time to carry out zeros on NO_x or Ozone instruments before security for the flight.

CO	Background ppbV became very high above FL150, resulting in unreliable data, especially during profile descent after calibration.
O₃	None
NO_x	No flow through Ozonator at FL150 and above therefore only NO channel available (no NO₂ or NO_x measurements). Flow did not recover on descent until FL110.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

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CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT #T6	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		15000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
100055	100150	25.32	23.2	0.17	0.31	0.49			S List base trace RI-1
		25.32	22.3	350	1549	1459	abandoned		D Adjuster
		25.29	21.32	200	304	1422			B base trimp
				2360	2361	2358			R between sample 1 & 2
				941.7	941.6	941.6			P still under way Baseline
		15000							
101405	101449	25.24	22.9	0.18	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S Retook sample
		25.23	22.18	391	437	656	672	623	D @ same height Run 1-2
		25.21	21.47	429	411	426	415	424	B [No Baseline
		25.22	20.57	2364	2367	2351	2343	2342	R adjuster
end	102555	24.58	19.08	941.7	941.7	941.7	941.7	941.8	P for this block.]
		3500		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
104847	104924	25.61	23.40	0.17					S Run 2.1
				591					D Run
				487					B abandoned
				2398					R due to cloud
				989.4					P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

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FLIGHT NUMBER: B DATE: 14/06/08 OPERATOR: B. GIDDINGS Page 1 of 2
 PROJECT: CAPEX

T6

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT # T6	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		1400		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
105438	105521	25-48	23.2	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S 1400' Run 3-1
		25-54	22.5	548	738	588	1456	1826	D
		25-48	21.6	470	481	487	405	586	B
		25-36	20.8	2398	2401	2398	2400	2411	R
		25-32	19.8	989.4	989.4	989.4	989.4	989.4	P
		1400'							
110548	110615	25-38	23.07	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S Run 3-1
		25-37	22.36	583	849	1081	1401	1630	D
		25-32	21.52	479	502	497	512	595	B
		25-24	20.76	2401	2404	2406	2411	2412	R
111236	111236	25-23	19.7	989.4	989.4	989.4	989.4	989.4	P
		1400'		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
111324	111358	25-31	22.99	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.08	S Run 3-1
		25-29	22.29	679	1118	1178	1550	1799	D
		25-22	21.43	472	465	475	491	572	B
		25-12	20.63	2404	2388	2380	2384	2399	R
112136	112136	25-15	19.51	989.4	989.4	989.4	989.2	989.2	P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

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FLIGHT NUMBER: B	DATE: 14/06/06	OPERATOR: B. GIDDINGS	Page 1 of 2
PROJECT: CAPEX			

CCN LOG

T6

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT # T6	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		9000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
113753	113846	25.31	23.05	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S Run 5.1
		25.32	22.32	520	483	890	1294	1575	D
		25.27	21.56	433	426	445	453	473	B
end @		25.27	20.73	2301	2379	2378	2377	2375	R
114836		25.	19.71	983.2	983.1	983.1	983.1	983.1	P
		9000							
114920	115010	25.21	22.29	0.17	0.31	0.49	0.71	1.07	S Run 5.1
		25.22	22.20	440	429	648	957	960	D
		25.16	21.38	413	397	401	402	431	B
end @		25.08	20.64	2358	2360	2355	2352	2349	R
1,5847		25.08	19.51	983.1	983.1	983.2	983.2	983.2	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B211

Date:

14 Jun 2006

Operator:

Joao / Doug

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet 90mm diameter type AC	Bottom inlet 90mm diameter type AC
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On (Z)	Time Off (Z)	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Ground	AC59	-	-	Top	08:53	09:13:40	-	2012	
Ground	AC60	-	-	Bottom	08:53	09:13:40	-	3804	
Filters run 1	AC61	-	-	Top	10:00:59	10:30:04	R1.1/2	1464	FL150 AC62 partly split & 2/3 loose R1.1 10:00:59 – 10:05:53 End of R1.1 "flow so far" Top: 263, Bot: 642 R1.2 10:07:34 – 10:30:04 Start of R1.1 "flow so far" Top: 346, Bot: 856
Filters run 1	AC62	-	-	Bottom	10:00:59	10:30:04	R1.1/2	3724	
Filters run 2	AC63	-	-	Top	10:48:47	10:52:23	R2.1	196	FL035 (or 3500') Aborted due to cloud base. Descended to lower level. Sample pipes closed during descent to prevent cloud contaminating filters. Flows not zeroed so totals below include this short run.
Filters run 2	AC64	-	-	Bottom	10:48:47	10:52:23	R2.1	314	
Filters run 3	AC63	-	-	Top	10:54:38	11:24:44	R3.1	(start) 249 - (end) 2351	Start value shows flow when sample pipes reopened at new level (1400' above sea level = 500' to 1100' radalt)
Filters run 3	AC64	-	-	Bottom	10:54:38	11:24:44	R3.1	(start) 392 - (end) 2262	
Filters run 4	AC65	-	-	Top	11:37:53	12:00:19	R4	1283	AC66 was damaged so not used. AC67 used instead FL090
Filters run 4	AC67	-	-	Bottom	11:37:53	12:00:19	R4	1190	
Ground	AC69	-	-	Top	12:21:50	12:38:45	-	1245	QNH 1010
Ground	AC70	-	-	Bottom	12:21:50	12:38:45	-	2862	
		-	-	Top					
		-	-	Bottom					

ARIES flight log

Flight: B211

Location: Beja, Portugal CAPEX

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Date: 14/6/06

Operator(s): Joss Kerr

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes: It's raining - in Portugal!

2cm

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sht	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
090211	Cond	B211B	CSD	71.1	31.1	22.4	-190.6	24.0	CH1	Cond test
094952	Area 1	B211C	CSD	70.9	30.8	16.2	-190.6	27.1	CH1	
100104	Luernoch 1.1	B211D	CSD	70.8	30.2	15.6	-190.6	27.0	N1x3	→ 1006
100359	" " 1.1	B211E	Open	70.3	31.2	12.3	-190.6	27.7	Z1x1	
100512	" " 1.1	B211F	CSD	70.9	30.8	9.9	-190.6	22.8	N1x1	
100622	End Pt-1	B211G	CSD	70.7	31.0	9.8	-190.6	23.3	CH1	
100740	R1-2	B211H	CSD	70.9	30.5	9.7	-190.6	24.0	Z1x1 N1x3	
101040	R1-2	B211I	Open	70.3	30.5	8.6	-190.6	22.6	Z1x1	- Fell over - rebound @ 2cm
101422	R1-2	B211J	CSD	69.3	30.5	5.8	-190.6		N1x2	- HBB = 60°C
101551	R1-2	B211K	Open	67.5	30.0	6.1	-190.6	21.3	Z1x2	
101713	R1-2	B211L	CSD	61.5	29.3	6.0	-190.6	20.2	CHx2	
101931	R1-2	B211M	CSD	61.1	28.2	6.3	-190.6	21.4	N1x8	turning @ end of views.
102227	R1-2	B211N	Open	66.2	25.6	5.8	-190.6	26.2	Z1x2	
102341	R1-2	B211O	CSD	61.1	24.9	5.2	-190.6	26.0	CHx2	
102456	R1-2	B211P	CSD						N1x8	wings not level near end. (10.28" →)
102852	U1-2 end	B211Q	CSD	66.8	22.1	5.6	-190.6	19.9	CHx2	
104110	R2.1	B211R	also	71.0	30.4	12.3	-190.6	22.1	CHx2	103431 - no frame software
104935	R2.1	B211S	Open						Z1x1 x8	B500 on 1010 mb.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B211

Location: Baja, Panama

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Date: 11/16/06

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution: 2

Gain A: 2

B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
105328	B2-1	B211T	close	71.0	31.1	17.6	-190.6	21.7	CH1 x 2.	
105446	B3-1	B211U	open	70.4	30.9	18.0	-190.6	22.1	Z1 x 8	ISO 57.10
105858	B3-1	B211V	close	71.1	31.4	21.3	-190.6	22.9	Z1 x 2	
105957	" "	B211W	open	70.2	31.0	21.0	-190.6	23.0	Z1 x 2	
110109	" "	B211X	close	71.1	31.0	21.6	-190.6	23.3	CH1 x 2	
110224	" "	B211Y	open						Z1 x 8.	
110619	" "	B211Z	close	71.2	32.1	23.3	-190.6		N1 x 2	
110720	" "	B211φ	open						Z1 x 2	
110845	" "	B2111	close	71.3	31.9	23.8	-190.6	24.5	CH1 x 2	
110902	" "	B2112	open			23.8	-190.6	24.6	Z1 x 8	
111357	" "	B2113	close	71.1	33.2	24.8	-190.6	25.3	N1 x 2	
111512	" "	B2114	open						Z1 x 2.	
111624	" "	B2115	close	71.0	33.5	25.1	-190.6	25.6	CH1 x 2.	
111737	" "	B2116	open			25.4	-190.6	25.8	Z1 x 8	
112139	" "	B2117	close	71.2	34.7	25.4	-190.6	25.6	N1 x 2	
112258	" "	B2118	open						Z1 x 2	shutter closed at start
112409	" "	B2119	open						Z1 x 2	
112511	end B3-1	B211A	close	71.0	35.2	25.1	-190.6	26.2	CH1 x 2	

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ARIES flight log

Flight: B211

Location: Baja, Panama

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Date: 11/6/01

Operator(s): Joss

Resolution:

Gain A: B:

Notes: RAPEX

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
112935	R4-1	C211B	CSD	71.0	33.6	24.9	-190.6	24.7	CH x 2	
113740	R4-1	C211C	CSD	70.9	31.4	22.6	-189.9	27.3	CH x 2 CH x 2	
113849	R4-1	C211D	CSD						N1 x 8	
114254	R4-1	C211E	open						Z1 x 2	
114408	R4-1	C211F	CSD	71.0	31.0	17.8	-190.6		CH x 2 N1 x 2	
114519	R4-1	C211G	CSD	70.9	30.8	17.8	-190.6	25.4	CH x 2	
114631	R4-1	C211H	CSD						N1 x 8	
115037	R4-1	C211I	CSD open						Z1 x 2	
115156	R4-1	C211J	CSD			15.8	-190.6	23.9	N1 x 2	
115310	R4-1	C211K	CSD	70.9	30.8	16.0	-190.6	24.4	CH x 2	
115425	R4-1	C211L	CSD	70.9	30.8	16.0	-190.6	24.9	N1 x 8	
115833	R4-1	C211M	open	70.5	30.8	15.1	-190.6	24.1	Z1 x 2 Z1 x 3	
120016	R4-1	C211N	CSD	71.0	30.9	14.6	-190.6	23.5	CH	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG	Date	14/6/06	Flight	B211	log pages
Operator(s)	JB	Campaign	CAPEX		
Departure	Beja	Arrival	Beja		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers					•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers					•
FERA on			at time		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	21°C	Ch 17	21°C	Ch18 20°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20 40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time		08:24
Initial target temperatures	Hot	292.1	Cold		291.8
Target heating					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time		08:27
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not Fitted				
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud	8/8	Precip	Yes	
	Surface	wet	Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)	
	Ch16 (40-44)	Ch17 (45-49)	Ch18 (40-44)	Ch19 (40-44)	Ch20 (44-48)
	43.8	34.0	38.7	40.7	41.7

Power changeover

Headset on before start		•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		•
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	•
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.211**.....

 Date 14/06/06.....

 Operator's name: Wilson.....

 Page 1 of 2

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
090000								Preflight OK. Wet Night & some GPU problems.
093945								T/O from Beja
100059	R1.1	FL150	9.6	3	38	—	5c	Start R1.1
100553	"	"	9.6	3	38	→	5c	end R1.1
100734	R1.2	"	12.6	3	39	↗	5c	Start R1.2. set water to +43
101359	"	"	13.5	3.1	83	—	43	
101700	"	"	14.6	2.6	89	→	43	set water to 34. RH5 @ 98%
102630	"	"	14.6	0.4	66	→	34	set water to +39. RH5 dropping.
103004	"	"	14.6	1.5	75	—	39	end R1.2. descending to 3500ft
								Will reboot PC this descent due to PSAP comms probs.
104059		063	14.6	48	86	—	39	PC back. PSAP now recording. Neph data now recording as B211a.
103052	P1	FL150						Start P1
104359		3500ft	12.3	67	92	—	39	end P1 @ 3500ft
104847	R2.1	3500ft	13.5	63	93	↘	39	start R2.1. Set water to ramp down to +8c
105223	"	"	14.2	66	76	↘	23	end R2.1
105438	R3.1	1500ft	14.3	82 *	74	↘	16	Start R3.1
110000	"	1500ft	14.5	78 *	72	↘	12	set water to +40c
110430	"	"	14.3	81 *	93	↘	40	set water to +17c. *Suspect no dry Neph RH.
111730	"	"	14.4	72 ? *	63	↗	17	set water to +39c.
112444	R3.1	"	14.2	79.7	89	↗	39c	end R3.1. Set water to +33c.

112200 * Suspect last night's heavy rain has found it's way into neph rosemount inlet. Dry neph reading 75%. RH1 & 3 54 & 36% respectively. GE says 15.1% at this level, 1500ft ASL.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B211	Date	14/06/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	1
Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS									
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0818						Laptop time set			
						Sws video u/s			
0830						Sws window cleaned, but it is raining... SHIMS not cleaned due to rain			
093822						T/o Beja			
0942			Zen +6	50	200	Sws ok	X		
0942			shims	50	200	Shims ok		x	
100054	R1.1	FL150	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, clear above, view of clouds	x		
100554			shims	50	200	End run		x	
100735	R1.2	FL150	Nad - 6	30	200	Start run, view of clouds	x		
101605	R1.2	FL150	Zen + 6	100	200	Short zenith view, clear above	x		
101818	R1.2	FL150	Nad - 6	30	200	Back to nadir			
103004						End run			
103052	P1	FL150	Nad - 6	30	200	Start profile			
104359		3500' qnh				End profile			
104847	R2.1	3500' qnh	Zen + 6	50	250	Between cloud layers run	X		
105223						End run			
105438	R3.1	1400' qnh	Zen +6	50	250	Just below cloud run	x		
105728	R3.1	1400' qnh	Nad - 6	50	250	Short nad view, clear below	X		
105943	R3.1	1400' qnh	zen + 6	50	250	Back to Zen, clear below	x		
110553	R3.1	1400' qnh	Nad - 6	50	250	Short nad view, clear below	X		
110752	R3.1	1400' qnh	Zen + 6	50	250	Back to zen	X		
111305	R3.1	1400' qnh	Nad - 6	50	250	Short nad view, clear below	X		
111511	R3.1	1400' qnh	Zen + 6	50	250	Back to zen	x		
1116			shims	50	200	Shims ok, cloud above		x	
112131	R3.1	1400' qnh	Nad - 6	50	250	View of ground			
112310	R3.1	1400' qnh	Zen + 6	50	250	Back to zen			
112444						End run			
112659	P2	1400' qnh	Zen + 6	30	200	Start profile, switch to nad at interrupt			
113752		FL080				End profile			
113752	R4.1	FL080	Nad - 6	30	200	Above cloud run			
115053	R4.1	FL090	Zen + 6	100	350	Short Zen view, clear above			
115224	R4.1	FL090	Nad - 6	30	200	Back to nad			
115841	R4.1	FL090	Zen +6	100	250	Short Zen view			
120017						End run, instruments off			
121403						Land Beja			

AFWA SW-NE MM5 45Km
 RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C)
 VALID:12Z14JUN2006

SW **NE**
Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.

AFWA SW-NE MM5 45Km
 RH(>70%) BARBS(KT)TEMP(C)
 VALID:18Z14JUN2006

SW **NE**

Note: Wind direction is relative to a compass (barbs to left indicate westerly wind), not relative to route of flight. Start point is always on left side of cross section, endpoint on right hand side. Model terrain drawn per route of flight.